

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific coordination, project management & sustainability

D8.11 Reports from Advisory Board and Ethics Report year 4

Lead contributor	1 – UMCU (UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT)
Other contributors	WP Leads 2 – ULST (UNIVERSITY OF ULSTER) 3 – UU (UPPSALA UNIVERSITET) 6 – i-HD (THE EUROPEAN INSTITUTE FOR INNOVATION THROUGH HEALTH DATA) 7 – KUL (KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN) 9 – LAREB (STITCHING LAREB) 13 – NUTH (THE NEWCASTLE HOSPITALS NHS FOUNDATION TRUST) 37 – JANSSEN (JANSSEN PHARMACEUTICA NV) 38 – NVS (NOVARTIS PHARMA AG) 39 – SANOFI (SANOFI-AVENTIS RECHERCHE & DEVELOPPEMENT) 41 – GSK (GLAXOSMITHKLINE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT LTD.) 47 – UCB (UCB BIOPHARMA SRL) 53 – Takeda AG (TAKEDA PHARMACEUTICALS INTERNATIONAL AG)

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Abstract

This deliverable contains the assessment, guidance, and recommendations from the members of the Advisory Board of ConcePTION on project activities and compliance of these activities with IMI regulations, ethics, and scientific standard procedures. It focuses on the progress of the project during the fourth year as well as the sustainability of ConcePTION and recommendations for finishing the project.

The feedback provided by each of the members of the Advisory Board is primarily based on the presentations and discussions which took place during the General Assembly meeting of ConcePTION in March 2023. Before this meeting, each Advisory Board member received some reading materials including the latest project publications, deliverables, a recording of a webinar on the ConcePTION webinar, and notes of the plans regarding sustainability. The current report also contains feedback and actions points provided from the Managing Team of ConcePTION.

The members of the Advisory Board agree that ethical standards for data collection, privacy protection and human participation are met in the ConcePTION project.

Advisory Board report

The aim of this deliverable D8.11 is to report to IMI on the assessment and recommendations provided by the Advisory Board (AB) on the fourth year of the project as well as their recommendations for finishing the project and the sustainability of the project. The feedback provided by each member of the AB is based on the presentations and discussions which took place during the General Assembly Meeting (GAM) of ConcePTION on March 27 and 28, 2023 as well as the reading materials received from PMO. The GAM provided the work packages with the ability to share their key achievements during the project and work on a roadmap on how to finish the work before the end of the project. During the GAM ConcePTION's sustainability activities and plans were also presented and integrated into the roadmap.

The members of the AB were invited to attend both meeting days. PMO sent a save-the data to each member a few months before the GAM and provided the reading materials and questions one month before the GAM. These questions form the structure of this deliverable and contains the recommendations and feedback provided by the AB members. Unfortunately, not all members of the AB could attend.

The questions provided to the AB are the following:

1. What would you recommend to the consortium to help them ensure that they can keep the ConcePTION ecosystem going after the project has ended?

2. Do you have recommendations for the consortium on how they can best engage with other initiatives on a global scale, in which close collaboration is facilitated and strategies are aligned?
3. What regulatory engagement strategies would you recommend to the consortium for the last phase of the project?
4. Do you have any other recommendations to the consortium specifically regarding the sustainability of the knowledge generation activities (Scientific Study Network (WP1, WP2, WP7 and WP8) and the Breastmilk Network)?
5. In addition to the comments from last year, do you have any additional recommendations to the consortium specifically the sustainability of the knowledge dissemination activities (ConcePTION app, the knowledge bank, and e-Health)?

The members of the AB provided a report containing recommendations, guidance, and questions to the ConcePTION consortium. The report provided by the members has been collected in one single report to be submitted to IMI as deliverable D8.11.

Recommendations from the Advisory Board members

1. What would you recommend to the consortium to help them ensure that they can keep the ConcePTION ecosystem going after the project has ended?

The SAB is recommending to keep the ConcePTION ecosystem going after the project. However, considering the existing structural and financial challenges, we do recommend to overview the project ecosystem and possibly identify those elements that are crucial to the system and/or that will be maintained due to the standard operations of involved institutions. These activities that would be the core of the ConcePTION ecosystem should be prioritized for maintenance and funding and later be a base for development of the full or even enhanced ecosystem.

Moreover, we also recommend, as it was mentioned during the discussion, upholding of the firewall in finance between knowledge generation subset of activities and knowledge dissemination elements.

The SAB also recommends using the upcoming time to develop a good sustainable governance structure that should identify the core activities of the ecosystem (mentioned above) and be responsible for future coordination and funding of the ecosystem.

The SAB shares the opinion that sustainability is likely to require public/private partnership. A platform for engagement with industry will require a governance/data access structure for ConcePTION that could be based on membership (i.e., an entry fee) to provide timely access to data sources and analyses for new drugs. Furthermore, and maybe even more importantly, such membership could provide access to data on the vast majority of most commonly used drugs which are "off patent". An alternative would be a fee for service structure which might

be a more difficult path for providing sustainability for ConcePTION. If a fee for service structure were adopted, some rapid method for assessing feasibility of addressing a given research question could be in place so that industry partners could be assured they are not going down a blind path (see also the answer provided at question 4). Perhaps some combination of these two approaches could be considered.

Members of the Managing Team (MT) replied to the recommendations provided from the Advisory board as follows:

This is very valuable input and confirms many of our assumptions, such as upholding of the firewall in finance between knowledge generation subset of activities and knowledge dissemination elements. Further analysis is needed by the sustainability team to investigate whether a governance/data access structure for ConcePTION could be based on membership. An important question is whether this would be acceptable for industry. EFPIA members have previously indicated this may not be feasible – however, there is a need to verify this. We find it an excellent suggestion to prioritize those elements that are crucial to the system and/or that will be maintained due to the standard operations of involved institutions.

2. Do you have recommendations for the consortium on how they can best engage with other initiatives on a global scale, in which close collaboration is facilitated and strategies are aligned?

The SAB recommends aligning with the scientific communities in low and medium income countries (LMIC) by granting researchers from those countries access to the ConcePTION ecosystem. Moreover, researchers from LMIC could provide data about pregnancy use of anti-malarian and HIV medication. This kind of alliance could have an important impact on how medication for endemic conditions like malaria or HIV are used in pregnant and breastfeeding women. There are many different institutions in the LMIC that already have their own well-established and functioning biobanks, well-trained personnel, strong ties with high income countries research institutions, and established funding (e.g., prof. Rose McGready at Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU), in Thailand conducts research on malaria in pregnant women, and her research indicate that early treatment can increase the outcome of the pregnancy). To our knowledge these institutions would be interested in cooperation, if there is a propose precise research aim and the scope of research is defined in advance (coming up with new research questions, pooling their data, or working on a clinical consensus).

We also recommend alliance and cooperation with researchers and institutions in the USA, Canada, and Australia.

Members of the Managing Team (MT) replied to the recommendations provided from the Advisory board as follows:

Thank you for these excellent remarks. We are currently looking into funding opportunities. This advice may be particularly important if funding is obtained from organization such as

WHO or the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, as they have a particular interest in low and medium income communities.

3. What regulatory engagement strategies would you recommend to the consortium for the last phase of the project?

The main challenge that we have identified is that there is a high need of knowledge in this field which very difficult to obtain. However, we reckon that pharmaceutical industry is incentivized or/and required by the regulatory authorities to provide data on pregnancy exposure and lactation, it can become more cooperative in this respect. To achieve this purpose early engagement with the regulative authorities is needed, e.g., EMA and follow up e.g., in developing the necessary guidelines.

It will be of importance to gain information in the next year from both EU and outside EU regulatory authorities about the acceptability of ConCEPTION products for inclusion in product labels, and the regulatory authorities appetite for encouraging/incentivizing industry to support research products on off-patent products. Similarly, there is an urgent need to understand the regulatory stance on the excellent work that has been done by ConCEPTION on establishing a protocol for focused and timely generation of data on neurodevelopmental outcomes following prenatal exposures.

The SAB recommends that the ConcePTION project makes the regulators aware of its scientific merits and capabilities, however, here also caution is recommended not to overpromise, but be realistic on what ConcePTION can deliver.

Members of the Managing Team (MT) replied to the recommendations provided from the Advisory board as follows:

We fully agree with these comments. The consortium is currently engaging with EMA, where multiple work packages are looking into the regulatory stance on the work that they have done, specific outcomes, and the ongoing developments within the ConcePTION project. We agree that we should be realistic on what can be delivered, not only in light of capabilities, but also considering the time and (human) resources available.

4. Do you have any other recommendations to the consortium specifically regarding the sustainability of the knowledge generation activities (Scientific Study Network (WP1, WP2, WP7 and WP8) and the Breastmilk Network)?

See response to Q1: the keywords are **essential elements** of the eco-system and elements that **normal operations**, which are maintained regardless cooperation in a ConcePTION project are important, and **governance structure** that is responsible for securing funding.

Moreover, we recommend that the ConcePTION provides not only tools, but also has a systematic way of quick assessment what this tool can deliver and how quickly. E.g., a list of general questions, research realms, research topics that can be asked quickly, and those that require more time and additional resources. This preparation should address a hypothetical scenario: a researcher wants to ask a question X, when she is developing a grant proposal; she can easily contact ConcePTION, and be provided with information about how ConcePTION can help, how much time it will take, and the description of that data package that could be provided, as well as the cost of cooperation.

The SAB shared the opinion that collaboration with OTIS on products for the Knowledge Bank and for initiatives with the Breastmilk Network would be highly beneficial to both groups.

Members of the Managing Team (MT) replied to the recommendations provided from the Advisory board as follows:

We share the opinion that there would be significant potential advantages for all involved in the collaboration with OTIS as suggested. We will look into this.

5. In addition to the comments from last year, do you have any additional recommendations to the consortium specifically the sustainability of the knowledge dissemination activities (ConcePTION app, the knowledge bank, and e-Health)?

We recommend that the knowledge-bank set up cooperation with the existing well-known publishing houses that already provide education on developing standards of pregnancy health care. Those entities have already well-established channels of communications with healthcare professionals, e.g., by periodicals, handbooks, or smartphone applications. For instance: a medical publishing house may have already existing bank knowledge that is available only to physicians, for free, based on their license identification. A physician regularly checks medical news, and uses smartphone applications, when she needs support in clinical decision making. We suppose that it would be difficult to change the habits of that medical professional and introduce a new product. But a cooperation with the publisher could be beneficial for all. We even stipulate that a publisher can also provide resources that are not available for ConcePTION. For instance a publisher in Poland, if interested in the knowledge bank, could provide translation for Polish, Ukrainian, and Russian (Polish publishing house *Medycyna Praktyczna*: [Medycyna Praktyczna \(mp.pl\)](http://medycyna.praktyczna.pl) publishes translated from English *Obstetrics evidence based guidelines* and *Perinatal and fetal evidence based medicine*, as well as issues materials in Polish, Ukrainian and Russian; it provides physicians with resources like smartphone applications with drug repositories, articles on state-of-art medical problems, organizes training conferences; similar for profit but well-grounded institutions exists also in Romania, Hungary, and other countries).

We also recommend that all educational materials will be developed in accordance with the existing standards for education in medicine, e.g., a in a form of medical case analysis, as well, as be accompanied by tests checking the knowledge. Moreover, cooperation with

institutions that develop standards of medical education should be established: [WFME Standards - World Federation for Medical Education](#).

Members of the Managing Team (MT) replied to the recommendations provided from the Advisory board as follows:

These are excellent comments for consideration. We will communicate this advice with the relevant people involved in the knowledge bank set-up and the e-learning platform. These are under continual development.